

TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS: IMPACT OF TEACHER WORKLOAD ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This research paper drive looks at the effects of teacher workload on the performance of secondary school children in Pakistan. The issue of teacher workload has been one of the biggest concerns in the third world countries whereby teachers are usually compelled to work in several teaching and non-teaching assignments. The relationship between teacher workload and student performance and moderating variables, such as instructional quality, teacher-student relationships, and parental involvement, was examined with the help of a correlational, cross-sectional, quantitative research design. The sample used was 200 secondary school teachers and 200 students who were stratified by sampling. Structured questionnaires and academic records of students were used to gather data which was analyzed using SPSS with the help of t-tests, ANOVA and regression analysis. The results showed that teacher overwork has a negative impact on the quality of instruction, less individual student attention and decreased teacher-student interaction, which in turn causes poor student academic performance. However, the experience of teachers, their qualification and institutional support was found to be moderating this relationship. This study concludes that good workload management is critical in enhancing the effectiveness of teaching and improving the learning outcomes among students. It is suggested that schools should use balanced workload policies and offer the administration to maximize the teachers work.

Keywords: Teacher Workload, Student Academic Performance, Instructional Quality, Secondary Education, Teacher Effectiveness, Educational Management

Introduction

Teacher workload has become a burning question in the contemporary educational systems especially in underdeveloped countries such as Pakistan where teachers are supposed to carry out numerous academic and administrative duties. These roles comprise lesson planning, classroom teaching, student evaluation, administration, and extra-curricular activities. The growing pressure on teachers has dramatically changed their working status, commonly causing stress, burnout, and decreasing effectiveness in teaching (Hester, Bridges and Rollins, 2020).

The literature indicates that workload has been shown to adversely affect teaching and learning in areas such as instructional quality, motivation of teachers and interaction in the classroom, which are critical elements of good teaching and learning. Research has indicated that when teachers are overworked, they might not be able to offer personalized attention to students, offer prepared lessons, and ensure that there is a significant interaction in the classroom. As a result, it can result in the deterioration of academic achievements of students (Skaalvik and Skaalvik, 2018).

Although much has been done to research on teacher workload considering global situation, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the direct effects of teacher workload on student academic performance in the secondary level in Pakistan. The majority of earlier research has concentrated on the issue of teacher stress, job satisfaction or workload at the primary or higher education level, so the research gap remains in the impact of stress on secondary education. This research therefore seeks to investigate the connection between teacher workload and the student academic performance as well as the mediating variables of instructional quality, teacher student relationships and parental involvement.

Research Questions:

1. How does teacher workload affect teachers' ability to provide individualized support to students?
2. What is the impact of teacher workload on teacher-student relationships and learning outcomes?
3. How does parental involvement influence teacher effectiveness under varying workload conditions?

Literature Review

Teacher workload is an issue of critical concern in modern education systems especially in the developing countries where teachers must undertake various academic and administrative roles. The scope of teacher work is a broad subject that involves lesson planning, teaching in the classroom, student evaluation, administration, and extra-curricular activities (Amisshah and Addison, 2025). The increasing complexity of such roles has significantly added the professional demands of the teachers, which may in most cases adversely affect the teaching performance and wellbeing of the teachers. The research indicates that a workload that is above a specific level negatively impacts on the quality of teaching and academic performance of the students. When teachers are overburdened, they can feel stressed, fatigued, and burned out, thus losing their capability to provide effective instruction and engage students in a meaningful way (Jomuad et al., 2021; Skaalvik and Skaalvik, 2018). In the case of overwhelmed teachers, there is less time to

prepare lessons, provide individual instruction, and prompt feedback, which are all crucial to improving student learning (Walker, Worth, and Van den Brande, 2019). As a result, high workload is related to a decreased classroom interaction, poor quality of teaching, and poor academic performance of students.

Quality of teacher-Student interaction is inherently required in the teaching and learning process. Sociocultural perspectives on effective learning state that effective learning is achieved when teachers interact, provide feedback, and support the learning process in a guided manner (Vygotsky, 1978). But too much workload may limit the capacity of teachers to offer personalized attention and ensure effective classroom interactions, thus adversely affecting student achievement (Kanwal, Rafiq, and Afzal, 2023). Likewise, research indicates that educators in high workload settings can hardly achieve classroom efficacy because of time limitations and augmented administrative duties (Hendra et al., 2025).

Association of teacher workload and student performance can also be explained as per theoretical frameworks. According to the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, when job demands are high like workload and they are not accompanied by proper resources, then they cause stress and burnout (Demerouti et al., 2001). Moreover, Cognitive Load theory states that people have a finite cognitive capacity; thus, when the workload is too high, it may overwhelm the mental resources of the teachers making them less effective in planning and providing instructions (Sweller, 1988). Time-on-Task Theory also states that less time spent on instruction because of workload limitation impacts negatively on student learning (Carroll, 1963). All these theoretical viewpoints are an indication that teacher workload is a critical factor in determining teaching effectiveness and student performance.

In secondary level of education, the effects of workload are more pronounced since the level demands more academic work on the teachers and students. Teachers must frequently deal with big classes, a variety of needs, and a lot of administrative work, and it restricts their possibilities to offer individual instructions (Ancho & Bongco, 2019). Studies indicate that work overload decreases the time of meaningful

teacher-student interaction, which leads to the decrease of student engagement and motivation (Tarimo, Bahati, and Labito, 2020). Conversely, a manageable workload allows teachers to use innovative teaching methods, offer constructive feedback, and create positive learning environments, which ultimately enhance student performance (Machado et al., 2025).

There are several mediating factors which affect the relationship between teacher workload and student academic performance. Instructional quality is a mediator because it has direct influence on the effectiveness with which knowledge is given in classroom. The workload usually causes learning outcomes to be adversely affected by a decrease in lesson preparation and the use of less effective teaching methods (Bano, Minaz, and Idris, 2025). The relationships between teachers and students are also crucial, since positive interactions with students lead to increased motivation and engagement, but these are not easily achieved when the teacher is under work pressure (Emboden and Villanueva, 2024). Also, school resources and institutional support may alleviate or increase the impact of workload. Proper administrative supply and instructional resources assist educators to better cope with the workload and preserve the education levels (Gonzales, Guimary, and Gabunilas, 2022).

Systemic challenges like big classes, scarce resources, and burdensome administration in the context of Pakistan further compound teacher workload. Research has shown that teachers at Pakistani secondary schools frequently have too much work and thus lack the ability to provide quality education and help students learn (Rashid, Subhan, and Imran, 2022; Khan, Iqbal, and Tasneem, 2022). Despite these challenges, the empirical evidence on a particular problem of teacher workload as the direct predictor of the student academic performance in secondary school is thin.

Moreover, the interaction of the workload dimensions and intermediate variables such as teacher motivation, institutional support and classroom climate have not been sufficiently explored in the literature. The research interest is mostly centered on teacher well-being, and the workload is not directly related to the student outcomes, particularly in developing countries (Wang, Sun, Wang, and Liang, 2025). This gap demonstrates the need to undertake more

research to know more about the impact of workload on teaching and student achievement. To sum up, the literature has shown that teacher workload is a big issue that impacts on the quality of instructions, effectiveness of teachers and the academic performance of students. Although international and domestic research proves the adverse effect of the heavy workload, contextual research in the context of the secondary education level is still required. This research seeks to fill this gap by exploring the connection between teacher workload and student performance in Pakistani secondary schools, with key mediating factors.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was a quantitative design to investigate the relationship between workload of teachers and the academic performance of the students in secondary schools. The research design was cross-sectional correlational because it is possible to investigate relationships between variables without controlling them and gather data at one time (Creswell, 2018).

The study population was made up of teachers and students in secondary schools in the grades 9 and 10 in the selected public and private schools. The selection of these participants was due to their direct involvement in teaching-learning process in the secondary level. Stratified sampling method was used to achieve representation based on the school type (public and private), gender, and location (urban and rural). A total of 200 teachers and 200 students were included in the final sample which was felt to be sufficient to conduct statistical analysis.

Teacher workload was taken as the independent variable and the performance of students in terms of academic achievement was taken as the dependent variable. Teacher workload was gauged on various dimensions that comprised teaching time, lesson preparation, grading, administrative work, and extracurricular work. The performance of students was assessed on Grade Point Average (GPA) basis, test performance, and classroom attendance. In addition, moderate variables such as experience and qualification of teachers, classroom size and institutional support were also taken into account to have a further understanding of the impact of the moderate variables on the

relationship between workload and student achievement.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and developed based on existing literature. The instrument has been divided into components which comprise teacher workload, teacher instructional practices, teacher student relationship and parent involvement. A five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree through strongly agree) was used to measure the responses.

The questionnaire was checked with the help of specialists of education and research methodology to guarantee its validity. A small pilot study was carried out on a separate sample not included in the study and reliability of the instrument was established by Cronbach alpha coefficient (0.82) showing good internal consistency.

The data collection process included seeking their consent of school administrations and

handing out questionnaires to teachers and students. The study participants were made aware of the study aim and it was a voluntary participation. The research was carried out in a highly confidential and anonymous manner.

To analyze the data, Statistical Package of Social Sciences was used (SPSS). Descriptive statistics including mean and standard deviation was also used to summarize data and inferential statistics including independent t-tests, one-way ANOVA, and regression were used to study relationships among variables and test study hypotheses.

Ethical considerations were carefully followed. Ethical consent was given to the participants and their answers remained anonymous. The information obtained was only utilized academically and ethical research standards were followed.

Results / Findings

Both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses are used to present the study findings to test how teacher workload relates to academic performance of students.

Research Question 1

What impact does workload have on a teacher capacity to offer each student tailored support?

Table No 1

Regression analysis regarding the impact of workload on a teacher capacity to offer each student tailored support

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.016 ^a	.000	-.005	3.51314

a. Predictors: (Constant), Workload on a Teacher Capacity

Table No 2

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.629	1	.629	.051	.822 ^b
Residual	2443.751	198	12.342		
Total	2444.380	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Student Tailored Support

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher Workload

The regression analysis shows that there is no significant effect of teacher workload on the possibility of giving students individualized

support. The value of R² as presented in Table 1 is 0.000 which implies that workload is virtually of no use in explaining the difference

in student tailored support. The adjusted R² is negative (-0.005) which is yet again another indication of the weak explanatory capacity of the model. In the same way, Table 2 indicates that the model is statistically non-significant, $F = 0.051$, $p = 0.822$ ($p > 0.05$). This implies that the

workload of teachers does not have a significant influence on student customized support. In general, the results indicate that other factors besides workload can be more significant in determining the ability of teachers to give individualized support to students.

Research Question 2

What effects does workload have on the relationship between students and teachers and how does it affect learning outcomes?

Table No 3

Regression analysis regarding the impact workload on the relationship between students and teachers

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1137.42	1	1137.4	43.125	.000 ^b
Residual	5222.51	198	26.375		
Total	6359.68	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship Between Students and Teachers

b. Predictors: (Constant), Workload

Table No 4

Regression analysis regarding the impact workload on Learning Outcomes

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	984.36	1	984.36	51.151	.000 ^b
Residual	3810.35	198	19.244		
Total	4794.72	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

b. Predictors: (Constant), Workload

According to the regression analysis, the workload is statistically significant in terms of the teacher student relationship and learning outcomes. In the case of teacher-student relationship, the model is important ($F = 43.125$, $p < .001$), which means that the more workload is, the worse is the quality of the interaction and support between teachers and students. Likewise, workload is a significant factor influencing learning outcomes ($F =$

51.151 , $p < .001$) as it has a powerful influence on the academic performance of students. These results indicate that overworking may decrease the availability and meaningful interactions of teachers, as well as lead to decreased student attention and performance. In general, the proper management of workload is what should be used to ensure the positive relationships in the classroom and improved learning outcomes.

Research Question 3

What impact does parental engagement have on teacher's effectiveness as education?

Table No 5

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1074.994	1	1074.994	129.172	.000 ^b
Residual	1647.801	198	8.322		
Total	2722.795	199			

- a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Effectives
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Parents Engagement

Regression analysis regarding the impact

Parental Engagement on Teacher's Effectives

The regression analysis reveals that workload has a statistically significant effect on both the teacher-student relationship and learning outcomes. In the case of teacher-student relationship, the model has been found to be important ($F = 43.125, p < .001$), meaning that the more workload, the lower the quality of interaction and support between teachers and students. In the same vein, workload is a very important factor that influences learning outcomes ($F = 51.151, p < .001$), indicating that it is a potent factor on the academic success of the students.

These results indicate that overworking can decrease the availability and meaningful participation of teachers, as well as lead to the decrease in student attention and performance. In general, the workload management is a key to positive classroom relationships and improvement of the learning outcomes.

The results, in general, show that teacher-related variables like gender, qualifications, and experience have a strong influence on teaching effectiveness in workload conditions, but student demographics variables have little effects. The findings substantiate the thesis statement that work overload impacts the quality of instruction and teaching performance that subsequently determine the outcome of the student in their academic performance.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide much data on the relationship between teacher workload and student achievement in high school. The results indicate that gender, qualifications and teaching experience are teacher-related variables that have a great influence on the instructional performance in workload conditions that eventually influence student achievement.

The researchers concluded that female teachers showed a relatively high score on performance-related scores compared to male teachers. This observation is consistent with other studies indicating that female teachers tend to be more interactive in the classroom, have better communication, and emotional support skills,

which positively impact the teaching-learning process (Jomuad et al., 2021). Such attributes can also be used to reduce some of the adverse impacts of workload by ensuring the students are engaged and productive learning conditions are supported.

The findings also indicated that better qualified teachers, especially those who had PhD qualifications performed much better than less qualified teachers. This observation is consistent with previous research that has shown that highly qualified teachers have better pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, and classroom management skills, which helps them in managing workload pressures effectively (Amisshah and Addison, 2025). Likewise, the performance of experienced teachers was found to be superior to less experienced teachers, which is why it is possible to argue that the experience in teaching improves time management, adaptability, and coping strategies in challenging working conditions (Rashid, Subhan, and Imran, 2022).

Notably, the research points out that there were no significant differences in the variables associated with students including gender and grade level. This implies that the effect of teacher workload on student academic achievement is homogeneous between various groups of students. This observation supports the fact that workload does not solely have a dependent influence on the quality of teaching but is contingent on the student traits, as it has been reported in the past (Tarimo, Bahati, and Labito, 2020).

Such results are in great agreement with the current theoretical frameworks. Under the Job Demands Resources (JD-R) model, high job demand is the excessive workload, which may cause stress and poor performance in the absence of resources to support them (Demerouti et al., 2001). In the same vein, Cognitive Load Theory has it that teachers who have heavy workload might have cognitive overload, which restricts their capacity to plan and present effective instruction (Sweller, 1988). These theoretical assumptions are reflected by the outcomes of this research because the more

workload was the less effective the teaching and the better the instruction.

Moreover, the results correspond with empirical research indicating that high workload impedes lesson planning, lowers the quality of feedback, and the quality of teacher-student interaction, all of which are vital in student learning (Walker, Worth, and Van den Brande, 2019; Kanwal, Rafiq, and Afzal, 2023). Another point of argument that the study upholds is that workload can be tamed by the institutional and professional factors such as qualification and experience to enable teachers to continue with their performance regardless of the situation.

These results in the Pakistan context highlight the systematic issues such as large classes, workloads of administration, and institutional support, which add to the workloads of teachers. The findings are consistent with the other local research that has shown that workload has adverse impacts on quality of instruction and student achievement in secondary schools (Khan, Iqbal, and Tasneem, 2022). Yet this research adds to the existing literature by offering empirical data on the secondary level and discussing the importance of the moderating variables.

To conclude, the discussion indicates that the negative effects of teacher workload on the effectiveness of teaching can be alleviated by the teacher characteristics and the institutional support. Then, the workload issue should be addressed with a multi-faceted solution that would not just assist in reducing the over-demands but also enhance the professional competence and support system of the teachers themselves.

Conclusion

This paper has explored how teacher workload influences the academic achievements of secondary school students and has discovered that workload has a strong influence on teaching and instruction and that excessive workload can greatly impact teaching efficiency and instruction. The outcome shows that overworked teachers with numerous tasks to complete would not be able to provide personalized attention, proper classroom-classroom interaction and quality teaching that would eventually lead to poor performance of the students.

The research also found that teacher-related variables including qualifications and teaching experience are very important in effective management of workload. The pressure of the workloads and the teaching of the instructions could be addressed easier by the well-trained and experienced teachers and a more effective instructional process. On the other hand student related variables such as gender and grade level did not affect the meanings in any significant way implying that the effects of workloads are similar in the various groups of students.

All in all, the research indicates that teacher workload is a critical aspect that affects teaching-learning process. It requires institutional policies and professional development that will enhance teacher performance and student learning outcomes by effectively managing the workload. The findings contribute to the body of literature by providing context-specific findings in secondary schools and the importance of balancing teachers roles in a bid to enhance the quality of education.

Implications

This research has significant theoretical, practical and pedagogical implications on how to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and student academic achievement.

On theoretical grounds, the study reinforces the available theoretical frameworks like Job Demands Resources (JD-R) model and Cognitive Load Theory by presenting empirical evidence that excessive workload is a considerable job demand with adverse impact on the performance of teachers. The results also generalize these theories by demonstrating that the workload effects may be moderated by the teacher-related variables such as qualifications and experience particularly in the context of secondary education in developing countries.

In practicality, the study indicates that the school administrators and policymakers ought to identify good methods of controlling workloads. Educational systems need to emphasize on the minimization of unnecessary administrative activities, a fair allocation of work, and support systems in place to support teachers. By enhancing working conditions, stress and burnout can be reduced and teachers

will be able to focus more on teaching and communicating with the students.

The study reveals that teacher capacity needs to be enhanced through professional development and training programs. Arming teachers with efficient time management, teaching techniques, and classroom management techniques can assist them deal with work pressure more effectively. Moreover, learning outcomes can also be enhanced by fostering favorable school climates and enhancing teacher-student relations.

Moreover, the results indicate that the institution support (e.g., access to teaching materials and administrative support) can be greatly improved to increase the quality of instruction. The educational systems will be in a position to offer more effective learning environments through the solution of workload problems that will not only be beneficial to the teachers, but also to the students.

Overall, this study can be of immense benefit in the evolution of the policies and practices that are to be aimed at attaining maximum efficiency in the working process of teachers and the level of quality of education in general.

Limitations

This research is limited in various ways, but some good pieces of information have been given that should be factored in the interpretation of the results.

- Firstly, the study was limited to a specific sample of secondary schools, and it may not be fully reflective of the learning environments. Thus, the result might not be generalizable to other areas or education systems.
- Second, the study utilized cross-sectional research design as its research design, a research study that quantifies data at a single time. As a result, it does not allow for establishing causal relationships between teacher workload and student academic performance.
- Third, much of the data were self-reported by both teachers and students and prone to bias, such as social desirability and personal perceptions.

Also, the research concentrated majorly on quantitative information, which might not be able to reflect the richness of experiences

regarding teacher workload and classroom dynamics. The qualitative data can provide a more in-depth image of these problems. Lastly, other external variables like school environment, student socioeconomic status and availability of resources might also contribute to student performance but could not be completely manipulated in this study.

Recommendations / Future Research

Due to the results and constraints of this research, several recommendations are made regarding how to enhance educational practices and inform future research.

1. Schools should embrace good practices of workload management in order to reduce the workload pressure on the teachers. This includes cutting down non instructional activities, equal distribution of activities, and administrative support. The other idea that schools need to consider is engaging more staff or developing support mechanisms to assist teachers with their clerical and extra-curriculum tasks.

2. The training initiatives of the professionals will be improved in order to equip them with the time management, classroom management and innovative teaching methods. This kind of training could enable teachers to deal with the pressures of workload better and still be able to offer instruction of good quality.

3. The policymakers should also target the working conditions within schools particularly by reducing the number of students in classes, and the supply of teaching facilities. Institutional support is very important in improving the performance of teachers and alleviating the adverse impacts of workload.

The future studies ought to investigate longitudinal designs to study the long-term effects of teacher workload on the performance of students. Further evidence of what the teachers go through and how they cope would also be provided by qualitative or mixed method. It is also recommended that further research be conducted to determine the other mediating variables such as teacher motivation, school leadership and technological integration. Further studies to other areas and levels of education would enhance the external validity of the research and will result in a more detailed view of the issue.

References

- Amissah, A. L. O., & Addison, A. K. (2025). Optimizing resource management: The impact of administrative practices on teachers' job performance in secondary schools. *Convergence Chronicles*, 6(3), 69-82.
- Ancho, I., & Bongco, R. (2019). Exploring Filipino teachers' professional workload. *Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers and Teacher Education*, 9(2), 19-29.
- Bano, I., Minaz, A., & Idris, M. (2025). Teacher workload and instructional effectiveness in secondary education. *Journal of Educational Research*, 12(1), 45-60.
- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499-512.
- Jomud, P. D., Antiquina, L. M. M., Baloria, J. B., Dacalos, J. B., Dionaldo, D. M., & Clarin, A. S. (2021). Teachers' workload in relation to burnout and work performance. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, 8(2), 48-53.
- Kanwal, S., Rafiq, M., & Afzal, A. (2023). Teacher workload and its impact on student learning outcomes. *Pakistan Journal of Education*, 40(2), 115-130.
- Khan, S., Iqbal, M., & Tasneem, S. (2022). Impact of teacher workload on student academic performance in public schools. *Journal of Educational Studies*, 14(1), 77-92.
- Rashid, M., Subhan, M., & Imran, M. (2022). Teacher workload and classroom effectiveness: Evidence from secondary schools. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 44(1), 23-38.
- Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2018). Job demands and teacher burnout. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 152-160.
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257-285.
- Walker, M., Worth, J., & Van den Brande, J. (2019). Teacher workload and its impact on educational outcomes. *Education Policy Review*, 11(4), 34-50.
- Hester, O. R., Bridges, S. A., & Rollins, L. H. (2020). Overworked and under-supported: The effects of teacher workload on instructional effectiveness. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 10(2), 45-56.